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Magnetic, Spectral and ESR Studies on Copper(II) Complexes of Cyclohexanone Thiosemicarbazone

SULEKH CHANDRA, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 10 April 1980, revised 18 September 1980, accepted 29 January 1981

TRANSITION metal complexes of thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones have drawn much attention due to their activity against small pox, virus diseases and certain kinds of tumour^{1,2}. In continuation of our studies on metal complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones³⁻⁶, we report in this paper the preparation and characterisation of copper(II) complexes of cyclohexanone thiosemicarbazone (chtsc) of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ and $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand was prepared by the method reported earlier⁶.

For the preparation of complexes, hot aquo-ethanolic solutions of hydrated metal salts and the ligand were mixed in molar ratio 1 : 2. The complex separated out in each case on cooling. It was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in an electric oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

All the complexes were insoluble in water and also in common organic solvents.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as a calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs unit, 20°). Electronic spectra were recorded on Russian $\text{C}\phi - 10$ automatic recording spectrophotometer. ESR measurements on polycrystalline samples were carried out using Varian $\text{E}_4 - \text{EPR}$

spectrometer, operating at ~ 9.4 GHz and 100 KHz field modulation and phase sensitive detection.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have composition $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}, \text{ClO}_4$ and $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$ (Table 1). Magnetic moments of all the complexes lie in the range 1.8-2.0 B.M. (Table 1), corresponding to one unpaired spin and suggesting monomeric nature of the complexes^{7,8}.

$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$ and CH_3COO) may be considered to have tetragonal structure with planar arrangement of two chtsc molecules around copper(II) and anions occupying axial positions. Similar copper(II) complexes are known for thiosemicarbazide⁹.

Tetragonal copper(II) complexes should involve the following three transitions of the positron $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$, $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_z$ and $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zx}, d_{yz}$. Bands due to these transitions usually overlap each other and one broad absorption band results¹⁰. Visible spectra of the complexes under discussion also show one such broad absorption band each (Table 1).

ESR spectra of polycrystalline complexes are shown in Fig. 1. All the complexes show anisotropic esr spectra with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ characteristic of tetragonal copper(II) complexes ($d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state). g -Tensor values have been calculated by Kneübuhl's¹¹ method and results are given in Table 1.

Recalling the tetragonal geometry of the complexes stronger interaction along Z-axis is to be accompanied by an increase in the value of g_{\parallel} . Strong axial bonding leads to increase in the length of the bond in XY plane, which results in a decrease of both in plane covalency and the energy

TABLE I—COLOUR, COMPOSITION, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND g -VALUES

Complex	Colour	Analytical data found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	G
		%M	%O	%H	%N					
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{Cl}_2$	Yellowish green	13.58 (13.32)	35.50 (35.25)	5.30 (5.45)	17.75 (17.62)	1.81	15200	2.193	2.043 2.029	3.7
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Yellowish green	12.12 (11.99)	31.50 (31.72)	4.95 (4.91)	21.25 (21.15)	1.95	15400	2.156	2.048 2.029	4.1
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Blue	10.60 (10.50)	—	—	13.70 (13.89)	1.81	16950	—	—	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Blue	12.40 (12.12)	41.39 (41.26)	6.18 (6.11)	16.20 (16.04)	2.01	16660	2.121	2.082 2.041	2.0
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{SO}_4$	Blue	13.00 (12.66)	33.67 (33.49)	5.25 (5.18)	16.97 (16.70)	1.87	16940	2.158	2.050	—

$$G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$$

Fig. 1. ESR Spectra of
 A. $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{Cl}_2$
 B. $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$
 C. $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{SO}_4$
 D. $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{OAc})_2$

of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition^{1,2}. Both these effects are the factors which tend to increase the value of g_{\parallel} . The g_{\parallel} values for the complexes studied (Table 1) follow the order, $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{Cl}_2 > \text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{OAc})_2$. Taking this to be the order of the strength of metal-anion interactions for chloride, nitrate and acetate, the result is in agreement with the respective position of the anions in spectrochemical series^{1,3}. A comparison of the g -tensor values of $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ with those of $\text{Cu}(\text{tsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Table 2) reveals the bonding in the two complexes to be of similar nature. The

For $\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2\text{SO}_4$, a five-coordinate square pyramidal structure may be suggested in analogy with the corresponding thiosemicarbazide (tsc) complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{tsc})_2\text{SO}_4$ for which the molecular structure has been determined¹⁸ by single crystal method. The copper atom is five-coordinate, the tsc molecules are bonded in a *cis* configuration, the two sulphur and two hydrazinic nitrogen atoms forming the corners of the base of square pyramid and the apex of the pyramid is occupied by an oxygen atom of the sulphato group.

TABLE 2

Complex	g_x	g_y	g_z	Ref.
$\text{Cu}(\text{chtsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.029	2.048	2.156	This work
$\text{Cu}(\text{tsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.0269	2.0474	2.1525	13

Schiff base formation^{1,4} is expected to cause lowering in the electron density on the hydrazinic nitrogen and hence a lowering in its donor ability. This effect should lead to comparatively stronger axial bonding as reflected in the relative values of g_{\parallel} for the two complexes. Further in an axial symmetry a parameter G defined as $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2) / (g_{\perp} - 2)$, is shown^{1,5} to measure the exchange interaction between copper centres in the polycrystalline solid. According to Hathaway if the value of G is larger than four, the exchange interaction is negligible while G values of less than four indicate considerable interaction in solid complexes. G values for the present complexes are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

Our grateful thanks are due to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for awarding a Senior Research Fellowship to one of us (S. C.).

References

- M. A. AKBAR and S. E. LIVINGSTON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 13, 101 and references therein.
- M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 15, 179 and references therein.
- S. CHANDRA, B. B. KAUL, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, 39, 2079.
- S. CHANDRA, K. B. PANDEYA, S. K. SINDHWANI and R. P. SINGH, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1980, 110, 207.
- S. CHANDRA, K. B. PANDEYA, G. L. SAWHNEY and J. S. BAIJAL, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 280.
- S. CHANDRA, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 476.
- B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 6, 37.

8. M. KATO, H. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 99.
9. A. CHIESI VILLA, A. GAETANI MANFREDOTTI and C. GUASTINI, *Cryst. Struct. Commun.*, 1972, 1, 207.
10. Y. NISHIDA and S. KIDA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, 27, 275.
11. F. K. KNEÜBUHL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1074.
12. D. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 3108.
13. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy' Elsevier Pub. Company, Amsterdam, 1968, 204.
14. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZESKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 396.
15. I. M. PROCTER, B. J. HATHAWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1968, 1678.
16. B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. BILLING, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 143.
17. R. J. DUDLEY and B. J. HATHAWAY, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 1795.
18. A. CHIESI VILLA, A. GAETANI MANFRIDOTTI and C. GUASTINI, *Crys. Struct. Commun.*, 1972, 1, 125.

Magnetic and Spectroscopic Studies on Metal Complexes of N-Phenyl-N'-p-Bromophenyl Thiourea. Part I.

M. R. CHAURASIA* and S. K. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. Post Graduate College, Dehradun

and

S. D. KHATTRI

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 14 August 1980, revised 27 July 1981, accepted 31 August 1981

THE following coordination compounds with N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea (L) have been prepared: $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 [$M=Ni(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Mn(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $X=Cl$, NCS , OAc] and ML_4X_2 [$M=Ni(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Mn(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $X=Cl$, NCS , NO_3]. The structure and bonding of the complexes have been studied by conductance data, magnetic susceptibilities, ir and electronic spectra. $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$ and ML_2X_2 types of complexes are tetrahedral whereas NiL_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 are square planar and octahedral respectively.

Experimental

Ferrous chloride was freshly prepared by the method described by Mellor¹. N-Phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea was prepared by the method of Bhargava and coworkers².

Preparation of $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 complexes: Ethanolic solution of the metal chloride, nitrate, thiocyanate or acetate were mixed with the ligand (L) in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 (M : L) molar ratio separately except in the case of $Hg(II)$ complexes which were prepared by mixing mercury salts and the ligand in acetone. The reaction mixtures were refluxed for 2-3 hrs. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the complexes were washed

with distilled water and a little ethanol. The complexes were dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. Analytical data, melting points, magnetic moments and stereochemistry of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND GENERAL BEHAVIOUR OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	m.p. (°C)	% Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		M	N	S	
NiL_2Cl_2	250	4.1 (4.3)	8.5 (8.2)	9.1 (9.4)	3.35
$NiL_4(NCS)_2$	135	4.1 (4.2)	9.8(10.0)	13.5(13.7)	3.36
CoL_2Cl_2	145	7.3 (7.6)	7.2 (7.5)	8.9 (8.7)	4.67
$CoL_2(NCS)_2$	146	7.2 (7.4)	10.3(10.6)	16.5(16.2)	4.65
CoL_4Cl_2	198	4.1 (4.3)	8.0 (8.21)	9.7 (9.4)	4.71
$CoL_4(NO_3)_2$	152	3.8 (4.1)	9.7 (9.9)	9.3 (9.1)	4.74
FeL_4Cl_2	130	4.0 (4.1)	8.0 (8.2)	9.6 (9.4)	5.40
MnL_2Cl_2	110	7.2 (7.4)	7.8 (7.6)	8.8 (8.6)	5.80
MnL_4Cl_2	111	4.3 (4.0)	9.6 (9.4)	8.5 (8.3)	5.67
ZnL_2Cl_2	82	8.5 (8.7)	7.2 (7.5)	8.3 (8.5)	dia
$ZnL_2(OAc)_2$	90	8.5 (8.2)	7.3 (7.0)	8.3 (8.0)	dia
ZnL_4Cl_2	92	4.9 (4.6)	9.7 (9.9)	4.8 (4.5)	dia
$Cd_2L_2Cl_4$	185	23.2(22.9)	8.0 (7.7)	6.7 (6.5)	dia
CdL_2Cl_2	200	14.3(14.1)	7.3 (7.0)	7.7 (8.0)	dia
$CdL_2(NCS)_2$	208	13.6(13.3)	9.7 (10.0)	15.0(15.2)	dia
CdL_4Cl_2	188	7.7 (8.0)	6.2 (5.9)	8.8 (9.1)	dia
HgL_2Cl_2	85	22.9(22.6)	6.2 (6.2)	7.5 (7.2)	dia
$HgL_4(NO_3)_2$	250	12.6(12.9)	9.3 (9.0)	8.5 (8.2)	dia

Molar conductance in nitrobenzene, ir spectra in nujol and electronic spectra (in nujol, ethanol or MgO) of the complexes were recorded.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are soluble in nitrobenzene. The low molar conductance values of $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 complexes show that these complexes are non-electrolytes³ having chloride, acetate, thiocyanate and nitrate coordinated to the metal ion. The magnetic data (Table 1) indicate tetrahedral geometry for ML_2X_2 and octahedral geometry for ML_4X_2 complexes⁴. ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 (with $M^{2+}=Zn, Cd$ and Hg) complexes are diamagnetic and show sp^3 and sp^3d^2 types of hybridization.

NiL_2Cl_2 shows the bands which can be assigned to the transitions: $15151 \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1A_{2g}$ (ν_1), $20,000 \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1E_g$ (ν_2) and $25,000 \ cm^{-1} \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1B_{1g}$ (ν_3). The electronic spectra of the NiL_4Cl_2 and $NiL_4(NCS)_2$ complexes show three bands at 8696 and 8700 cm^{-1} , 13889 and 13900 cm^{-1} and 25640 and 25700 cm^{-1} respectively. The above bands may respectively be attributed to $^5A_{2g} \rightarrow \ ^5T_{2g}$ (F), $^5T_{1g}$ (F) and $^5T_{1g}$ (P) transitions in the octahedral environment of the metal ions. The bands observed at 5550 and 5600 cm^{-1} , 15100 and 15120 cm^{-1} in the spectra of CoL_2Cl_2 and $CoL_2(NCS)_2$ are due to the $^4A_g \rightarrow \ ^4T_1$ (F) and 4T_1 (P) transitions⁵ respectively. Three bands observed at 9600, 20000 and 21739 cm^{-1} in CoL_4Cl_2 and at 9616, 19607 and 21459 cm^{-1} in $CoL_4(NO_3)_2$ complexes are typical of $Co(II)$ complexes in octahedral⁶ environment and may be assigned to the transitions $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow \ ^4T_{2g}(F)$, $^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. In FeL_4Cl_2 , a